

Research Letters

To Cite:

Rehman, W.U., & Khan, M. A. From Margins to Mainstream: A Longitudinal Analysis of Women's Empowerment in Pakistan and the Role of International Tourism 2023; Vol 1, Issue 1, pp. 27-46.

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

²Department of Forestry & Wildlife Management, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

Corresponding Author

Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

Email: wasikhan2@gmail.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 15th October, 2023

Reviewed & Revised: 17/ October/2023 to 13/December/2023

Accepted: 14th December 2023

Published: 15th December 2023

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

Research Letters

pISSNxxxx-xxxx; eISSNxxxx-xxxx

URL:<https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/journal-research-letters>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

From Margins to Mainstream: A Longitudinal Analysis of Women's Empowerment in Pakistan and the Role of International Tourism

Wasi ur Rehman^{1*} & Muhammad Asif Khan²

ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of international tourism, female literacy, female participation rate, gender disparity in health, women's access to finance, and economic growth on women's empowerment in Pakistan. The analysis is conducted using data from the period spanning 1975 to 2020. The findings of the study reveal that international tourism plays a significant role in promoting women's empowerment. However, gender disparity in health, education, access to finance, and economic growth hinders women's empowerment in the country. Consequently, it is crucial for the government to focus on reducing gender disparities in health to empower women effectively. Furthermore, the government should create more opportunities for women to participate in the financial market, as this can contribute to improving their livelihoods. Efforts should be made to attract more foreign visitors to the country, as this can generate additional revenue and foster women's empowerment, particularly in tourist destinations.

Keywords: Women empowerment; International tourism; Financial development; Gender disparity; Economics growth; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The inclusion of women in the tourism industry and their social empowerment can have positive effects on the industry itself and foster a greater sense of community among residents. Efforts should be made to increase the number of female entrepreneurs, as their participation in entrepreneurship remains relatively low compared to their male counterparts. Additionally, the income generated by women in the industry is often limited due to slow business growth, and they may also face a higher risk of business failure. Research indicates that women worldwide have made significant contributions to the tourism sector, indicating their capability and potential for success in this field (Samad & Alharthi, 2022). The idea of financial independence leading to lasting changes in women's status is subject to debate, and further long-term research is necessary to explore this notion. However, evidence suggests that financial and social independence gained through the tourism sector serves as a crucial catalyst for challenging prevailing gender ideologies. The cumulative effect of changes in gender norms, identities, and relationships contributes to a broader transformation of gender ideology as a societal institution (Kinnaird & Hall, 1996).

SHERWAN

Publishers

Intangible cultural heritage, encompassing elements like oral traditions, performing arts, rituals, festive occasions, and traditional crafts passed down through generations, holds great significance for cultural tourism. In rural areas, where resources and educational opportunities are often limited, rural women play a crucial role as custodians of such intangible cultural assets. However, these women also tend to be among the most vulnerable populations in rural societies due to their lower socioeconomic status and fewer livelihood options. Global development organizations, such as UN Women, the Association for Women's Issues in Development, and the International Center for Research on Women, are exerting pressure on governments to implement educational policies that promote gender balance. The establishment of women's clubs in 1925 played a pivotal role in enhancing women's involvement in society. These clubs initiated educational programs, established bookstores, hospitals for women and children, healthcare divisions, law offices, vocational training centers, arts and crafts initiatives, and more. In rural areas, "peasant houses" served as protective centers and women's clubs, contributing significantly to the fight against harassment and underage marriages. Female illiteracy was identified as a barrier to the economic and cultural advancement of the republic, as recognized by a special resolution adopted by the Central Auditing Bureau of the Russian Communist Party in March 1925. Overcoming this challenge required concerted efforts and time to change public perceptions. Additionally, the pressure from the administration for women's liberation, radical actions, and their involvement in public life, including participation in labor strikes, resulted in both positive outcomes and misunderstandings that led to setbacks. Despite these challenges, women enjoyed certain benefits, such as the ability to start work two hours earlier and receive full wages (Nasridinbekovna, 2022).

Gender discrimination and societal norms play a significant role in hindering women's access to higher education and their overall empowerment. In many cultures, patriarchal social norms restrict women's decision-making abilities, making it challenging for them to enroll in higher education. Factors such as education, unemployment, financial independence, social and cultural constraints, and economic opportunities greatly influence women's empowerment. Research has shown a strong correlation between these factors and increased societal engagement. The situation in Pakistani culture reflects the challenges faced by women, where men predominantly control the means of production, and women are confined to the home, leading to their subjugation and exploitation both privately and publicly. Long-standing societal norms perpetuate male dominance while undermining female power. Marxist feminism sheds light on the subordination and oppression experienced by women within the family and in relation to private property. Based on these assumptions, it is evident that women face obstacles in various areas, including accessing higher education (Naz et al., 2020). Esther Duflo, a Nobel laureate in economics, and Amartya Sen, another Nobel prize winner, both emphasize the importance of empowering women for growth and development. Duflo argues that empowering women can serve as a powerful catalyst for economic growth. Sen's "capacity" approach to development highlights the significance of creating an institutional environment that fosters freedoms and agency for individuals to pursue their aspirations for success. Sen particularly emphasizes that lack of autonomy, especially among the poor and women, hinders economic growth. Researchers have approached the topic of gender and development from various angles over the past few decades. Empowered women tend to report higher levels of life happiness, self-worth, and effectiveness. The liberation of women from social structures that restrict their agency has the potential to drive growth through private decision-making processes within households and by influencing public institutions.

The freedom to make their own decisions also plays a role in women's ability to take care of their health and access medical services. However, the level of independence and decision-making capacity for women varies across different communities, particularly in developing or low-income countries. Although there is no universally accepted definition that encompasses all aspects of women's independence, it is a topic widely discussed in research, particularly concerning reproductive health issues. Female autonomy is considered crucial in various healthcare contexts, including seeking and utilizing medical care and making decisions about treatment options. Evidence suggests that women's independence and control over healthcare decisions are often constrained in low-income or developing nations (Hornset et al., 2022; Cajamarca et al., 2022). Goal 5 of the UN Development Agenda, which focuses on gender parity and women's autonomy, continues to face challenges in nearly every region of the world. Achieving gender equality and empowering women is not only essential for basic human rights but also serves as a fundamental pillar for global prosperity and peace. The UN Sustainable Development Goals, including Goal 5, are crucial in advancing worldwide peace and harmony. By striving to create a world where both men and women have equal opportunities in education and employment, Goal 5 plays a significant role in transforming our world. However, the reality is that Goal 5 is lagging in many regions, which poses a setback to the broader sustainable development objectives. Addressing gender disparities and promoting women's autonomy is necessary to overcome these challenges and create a more equitable world. Travel and tourism have been shown to offer women greater prospects for empowerment in comparison to other sectors, thereby assigning the industry a heightened role in advancing the status of women. According to the UN Global Report on Women and Tourism in 2010, jointly conducted by the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and UN Women, the tourism sector affords improved avenues for women's engagement in the labor force, the establishment of women-owned businesses, and women's leadership positions when compared to other segments of the economy.

Opportunities for economic, social, and personal development are all areas in which inbound tourism may significantly empower women. Tourists from other countries spend money in the host country and boost the economy by buying goods and services there. The hotel and tourist industry, which has historically provided many job opportunities, including those open to women, stands to grow in response to this increased demand. As visitors interact with residents, cultural exchanges occur, creating a more tolerant and accepting community. As a result of this connection, many women have found success in careers as tour guides, craftspeople, business owners, and service providers. They can become more financially self-sufficient, and their confidence, abilities, and social circles benefit from these changes. By providing opportunities for financial security and individual growth, inbound tourism is a driving force in the advancement of women and the promotion of social justice and inclusion.

This research adds to the existing body of knowledge by analyzing the variables affecting women's empowerment in Pakistan in great depth. It addresses a knowledge vacuum in the field by recognizing the importance of foreign tourism to the empowerment of

women and calling for further study into the processes at play. The study also highlights the need for more research on gender gaps in health, education, access to finance, and economic development by addressing the dearth of in-depth analysis and quantitative data in these areas. Based on the research objectives, here are the corresponding research questions:

I. Does inbound tourism contribute to improving the economic well-being of women?

- a. How does the growth of inbound tourism impact women's economic opportunities and income generation?
- b. What are the specific sectors within tourism that provide employment and empowerment opportunities for women?
- c. What are the challenges and barriers that women face in accessing and benefiting from tourism-related economic activities?

II. What is the impact of education, health, and the labor market on women's empowerment in Pakistan?

- a. How does educational attainment influence women's empowerment in terms of decision-making, economic participation, & social status?
- b. What role does women's access to healthcare and reproductive rights play in their empowerment?
- c. How does the labor market participation and opportunities affect women's empowerment and agency in Pakistan?

III. Does women's access to finance and continued economic growth enhance their independence in socio-economic affairs?

- a. How does women's access to financial services, such as microcredit or savings programs, influence their ability to make independent decisions regarding economic matters?
- b. What are the effects of economic growth on women's independence in terms of financial decision-making, asset ownership, and economic participation?
- c. What are the key factors that facilitate or hinder women's access to finance and their ability to leverage it for greater independence?

These research questions guide the investigation into understanding the relationships between education, health, labor market, inbound tourism, finance, economic growth, and women's empowerment and independence in Pakistan. Conducting empirical research, data analysis, and gathering qualitative insights can provide valuable findings and contribute to the existing knowledge on these topics.

The following are the research objectives of the study, i.e.,

1. To examine the impact of socio-economic factors including inbound tourism on women's empowerment in Pakistan.
2. To assess the role of finance and economic growth on women's independence in a country, and
3. To evaluate the role of labor market reforms on women's status in a country:

These objectives provide a comprehensive approach to understanding the factors influencing women's empowerment, independence, and status in Pakistan, considering various socio-economic aspects and policy interventions. Conducting research on these objectives can contribute to the existing knowledge on women's empowerment and provide insights for policymakers and stakeholders to enhance gender equality and promote women's rights in the country. The motivation for conducting research on women's empowerment in Pakistan is evident from the challenges and gender disparities faced by women in various sectors. The existing gender gap, discrimination, and limited opportunities for women highlight the urgency to investigate the factors that contribute to women gaining political power and overall empowerment. Some key motivations for conducting this research include:

- I. Pakistan ranks low on global gender indices, indicating significant gender inequalities and discrimination. Understanding the factors that contribute to women's empowerment can help address these disparities and promote gender equality.
- II. Women working in the public and private sectors, especially in the informal economy, often face low pay, long working hours, lack of benefits, and job insecurity. Investigating the role of finance and economic growth in women's independence can shed light on potential solutions for improving their economic well-being.
- III. Women entrepreneurs face additional hurdles in accessing business opportunities and succeeding in male-dominated industries. Researching the barriers to entry and identifying strategies to promote women's entrepreneurship can contribute to their empowerment and economic advancement.
- IV. Women's political representation and participation in decision-making processes are crucial for achieving gender equality. Investigating the factors that impact women's access to political power can inform efforts to enhance their participation in politics and governance.

By conducting research on women's empowerment in Pakistan, the aim is to generate evidence-based insights that can inform policies, programs, and interventions to address gender inequalities and promote women's empowerment in various spheres of life. Ultimately, the goal is to contribute to the improvement of women's rights, opportunities, and overall well-being in Pakistan.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is divided into different sub-section; aim to review in-depth earlier studies to reach some conclusive findings.

2.1. Women empowerment through expansion of inbound tourism

(Seyfi et al., 2023) examines the financial independence of women in Iran's tourism and hospitality sector, considering the gendered consequences of economic restrictions and the societal context. The findings highlight the fragility of women's independence in Iran's religion-patriarchal society and the adverse impact of economic sanctions. Economic independence is identified as a significant factor in women's overall empowerment. The study emphasizes the need to address financial independence within the broader social movement for women's empowerment. (Syed et al., 2021) investigates the impact of global political risk (GPR) on inbound tourism to the BRICS nations from 1995 to 2019. The research reveals that country risk has a negative effect on inbound tourism. The study adds

to the understanding of the variables influencing incoming tourism and supports the development of inbound tourism policies. The analysis utilizes panel regressions and the enhanced mean group (EMG) estimation method to examine the diverse ways GPR affects inbound tourism across different percentiles. (Zhang & Yan 2022) examines the relationship between women's rights and tourism in 36 Asian countries from 2006 to 2019. Using the error correction model, the researchers find that tourism has a significant long-term positive effect on women's economic independence, employment opportunities, and education. While the impact of inbound tourism on gender equality may not be immediate, over time, it contributes to improving women's rights and reducing gender inequality. The study highlights the importance of factors like education and job opportunities alongside tourism in achieving gender equality. (Jackman, 2022) investigates the connection between inbound tourism and women's rights in the labor market using panel data from 143 nations between 2006 and 2017. The findings reveal that the impact of inbound tourism on women's rights varies across regions. In industrialized nations, there is a positive correlation between inbound tourism and women's rights, while in Sub-Saharan Africa, the correlation is negative. The study emphasizes the significance of considering the role of inbound tourism in promoting gender equality and women's economic independence. (Kumar et al., 2021) focuses on India's economic development and the role of inbound tourism in generating foreign currency profits. Using annual data from 1991 to 2019, the research shows that tourist receipts have continuously increased over the years, contributing to India's economic growth. Inbound tourism serves as a significant source of foreign currency and supports the expansion of major industries. The findings highlight the growth in global earnings from foreign travel and the contribution of Indian tourist revenue to worldwide tourism revenue.

(Sayira et al., 2021) centered their book on the experiences of Muslim women in relation to tourism. The authors argued that Islam has a more significant socio-cultural influence on women compared to men, especially within Muslim nations. The study examined the challenges faced by Muslim women working in the tourism industry, Muslim women traveling abroad, as well as non-Muslim women visiting Muslim countries. The aim was to provide an influential perspective on the examination of the interactions between gender, self-identity, and the concept of the "Other" from 1893 to 1993. The study presented a fresh analysis of an early book written by a Western woman that explored the Arab world and its people. The conclusion summarized the ten key findings of the chapters and offered recommendations for future studies on women and tourism in Muslim Asian nations. (Bhandari et al., 2022) conducted a research study in Nepal, specifically focusing on Sirubari Village in Syangja, to explore how domestic tourism supports local businesses. The study had three main objectives: to analyze the pattern of inbound tourism over the past five years, to examine the contribution of the hospitality and tourism industry in promoting local businesses, and to assess visitor satisfaction as a result of tourism in the village. The researchers gathered and analyzed data related to the number of tourists visiting Sirubari, their expenditure patterns, investment, and satisfaction levels with the hospitality services. The study revealed that domestic tourism had a more significant impact on the village compared to foreign tourism due to limited visibility and advertising. Financial empowerment and the preservation of local culture and the environment were identified as key motivators for the establishment of hospitality services. Women played a significant role in operating homestays, with a majority of men seeking employment overseas. The village provided various lodging amenities to accommodate the increasing number of visitors. (Zhang & Jiekuan 2020) conducted a study using data from 36 Asian nations between 2006 and 2018 to examine the relationship between the tourism industry and women's rights. Employing a system generalized technique of moments estimate approach, the research findings demonstrated a strong positive impact of tourism on women's equality. Asian nations exhibited the most substantial and statistically significant effects, followed by west and central Asian nations, and then south Asian nations. The study highlighted the need for multidisciplinary research on women's rights within the tourism industry to further advance this field, particularly in light of ongoing feminism and women's awareness movements. (Haq et al., 2019) investigates how socio-economic factors impact households' engagement in and spending on recreation and tourism activities in Pakistan. The findings indicate that factors such as income, education, region, and women's empowerment contribute to a higher likelihood of households participating in recreational and tourism activities. Conversely, having more adults and children in the household decreases the probability of participation. Moreover, household income and the age of the household head positively influence household expenditure on tourism, whereas having more adults and children in the household has a negative effect.

2.2. Women empowerment by opportunities to join labor force

(DeBrauw et al., 2021) conducted a study to examine how changes in the labor market could impact outcomes related to women's labor participation and autonomy. The research utilized a comprehensive panel dataset on jute producers in the Bangladeshi delta and collected information through farmer surveys conducted in four districts of Bangladesh. The findings indicate that while increased immigration may lead to changes in women's roles in farming, this process takes time. The surveys were conducted from 2017 to 2018. The study emphasizes the need for a better understanding of women's roles in rural labor markets, particularly in areas experiencing rapid urbanization. The study also reveals that there continue to be differences in test scores between men and women, with lower levels of empowerment reported by females compared to males. (Asadullah & Niaz, 2021) observed that while women's participation in the labor market is declining in many emerging countries, women's involvement in farming is increasing globally. However, the assessment of the research reveals that working in agriculture has not yet led to significant changes in women's lives or empowerment. The study suggests that substantial policy changes are necessary in the agriculture industry and elsewhere to enhance women's empowerment and household food security. These changes should include economic recognition of women's labor and a shift in societal norms to promote shared responsibility between men and women within marriages. The successful inclusion of women in agriculture will contribute to global food security when it becomes a means of achieving their independence. (Wang & Naveed, 2021) conducted a study exploring the relationship between economic inequality and female autonomy. The research specifically examines whether advancing women's political, social, and economic rights can reduce income disparity. The study also discusses the effects of women's empowerment on income disparity in economies known for their income disparities. Data from 134 countries spanning the

period from 1945 to 2015 were analyzed. The results indicate that empowering women in all three dimensions (political, social, and financial) has a significant impact on reducing income disparity. The impact of women's rights on income disparity varies across economies based on their wealth classification. Higher-income countries experience a much greater reduction in income disparity (twelve times) when female social and political power increases, compared to middle- and lower-income economies.

(Ghosh et al., 2021) conducted a study focusing on female empowerment through agriculture in Chapainawabganj, a district in Bangladesh. The study aims to determine the level of empowerment among women in the area and understand how specific factors contribute to their empowerment. Data for the study were collected during the period of 2020 and 2021. The main findings reveal that a significant proportion of respondents belonged to small-sized families, with up to four members, and a majority (60%) had no formal education. Most respondents were middle-aged and employed in the agricultural sector. The study highlights that despite not owning land, the majority of respondents earn a living through crop cultivation, livestock raising, and odd jobs. They face limitations in accessing education, government or non-profit assistance, and agricultural training, and lack cosmopolitan opportunities. (Wejnert, 2021) provides a critical analysis of market-based development factors that are relevant to women's rights, including market-based development objectives, workplace organizational structures, and social provisions. The study presents a theoretical framework that combines these factors interactively to understand women's rights in the context of market-based growth. The research covers the period from 1970 to 2000, and the conclusions discuss the significance of the developed theoretical model and the demonstrated gender inequalities in the impacts of female labor market-based development. The study highlights the importance of this framework for future academic investigations and policymaking, addressing the challenges posed by labor market-based development. (Aziz et al., 2022) conducted a study aiming to explore the reasons behind women's exclusion from the formal economic system in South Asian countries. The study covers the period from 2004 to 2017. The research findings suggest a close association between gender and the use of financial institutions. It was observed that women are less likely than men to have a bank account in countries where religious constraints limit their participation in the workforce. Conversely, countries that support women's rights and have strong regulatory frameworks tend to have a higher number of economically engaged women. The study emphasizes the importance of increasing female autonomy through government initiatives in South Asian nations. (Mubeen et al., 2022) focused their research on married Pakistani women aged 15 to 49 and examined their reproductive decisions. The study utilized data from the most recent Pakistan Health Survey (2017-2018). The findings highlight the significance of women's involvement in the female labor force for maintaining balanced fertility and decision-making within households. The study challenges previous beliefs by suggesting that indicators of female autonomy in developing countries, such as household decisions regarding labor force participation and education, are more crucial than knowledge about and use of contraception. Urban women, educated women, and those free of debt are found to have higher levels of autonomy and decision-making power.

Mubeen et al. (2022) aimed to investigate whether granting women the freedom to choose their own business ideas empowers them, promotes entrepreneurship, and enables their full participation in income-generating activities. The study utilized data from the 2017-2018 Pakistan Survey of Demographics and Health to analyze the relationship between women's economic autonomy, entrepreneurship, and household dynamics. The findings indicate that literate and employed women have higher levels of empowerment compared to unemployed women. The study emphasizes the importance of women's economic growth for overall financial and economic development. (Kusumawardhani et al., 2023) conducted a study analyzing the effects of internet accessibility on women's labor market outcomes in Indonesia. The research focused on the different impacts of internet accessibility on female labor market outcomes across various employee subgroups. The study covered the time period from 2007 to 2018. The findings indicated that the influence of internet accessibility on women's labor market outcomes is not always positive for females with a low level of education. However, there was still a positive influence on the labor participation rate, with stronger impacts observed in higher quintiles. The study highlights the benefits of internet accessibility, including the opportunity to prepare for and obtain flexible working conditions. It suggests that female-friendly workplace conditions and suitable IT infrastructure are essential components for fully utilizing the potential of the internet to assist women in achieving more advantageous labor market outcomes. (Saqfalhait et al., 2023) conducted a study examining the effects of trade liberalization on gender disparity and gender development indicators in Arab countries. The research utilized data from 1995 to 2020, focusing on two groupings of Arab nations based on their economic levels. The study found that trade liberalization, as assessed by globalization trade and taxes, had varying effects on gender development outcomes in the two groups. Higher taxes and women's unemployment were found to slow down certain aspects of development, while higher growth rates over time were associated with positive gender developmental outcomes. The paper's conclusion explores these findings and investigates whether the impacts of trade liberalization differ based on the economic levels of the countries involved.

2.3. Women empowerment through female access to education and health

(Rettig & Fick, (2018) aimed to develop and apply a comprehensive Female Empowerment Index (FEMI) to capture spatial and temporal variations in women's empowerment in Nigeria. They analyzed data from 2008 to 2014 and constructed the FEMI, which encompasses economic, social, and political dimensions of women's empowerment. The study concluded that promoting women's education, employment, and income is crucial for improving women's empowerment in Nigeria. They emphasized the need for policies and interventions that address cultural factors, such as religion and patriarchy, to promote gender equality. Education, employment, and household income were identified as strong predictors of women's empowerment in Nigeria. (Wei & Sarker, 2021) focused on investigating the relationship between women's empowerment and poverty reduction in rural areas of Bangladesh, specifically examining health, education, and living standards. The study aimed to identify the determinants of women's empowerment and examine its impact on poverty reduction. Using data from a 2015 survey in two rural districts of Bangladesh, the study found that women's empowerment, particularly in terms of education, access to healthcare, and decision-making power within

the household, has a significant and positive impact on poverty reduction. The paper concluded that investing in women's empowerment is crucial for poverty reduction in rural areas of Bangladesh, and gender-based policies and programs can play a significant role in promoting women's empowerment and poverty reduction. (Reshi & Sudha, 2022) emphasize that women's empowerment encompasses various factors, including education, employment, healthcare, and political representation. Education is highlighted as a fundamental aspect that plays a crucial role in promoting women's empowerment by equipping them with necessary skills and knowledge to actively participate in society. The conclusion of such a study would likely summarize the key findings and provide insights into the implications of these findings. It may also identify areas where further research is needed to better understand women's empowerment and make recommendations for policies or programs aimed at promoting gender equality.

(Brayerman-Borstein et al., 2023) aimed to examine the relationship between gender inequality, women's empowerment, and adolescent birth rates in Latin American cities. The study found a positive association between gender inequality and adolescent birth rates, while women's empowerment was negatively associated with adolescent birth rates. The authors concluded that reducing gender inequality and promoting women's empowerment could help lower adolescent birth rates in Latin American cities. They suggested that interventions focusing on education, healthcare, and women's rights could be effective in achieving these goals. The study used data from various sources, including DHS surveys conducted between 2005 and 2017, and GDI data from 2017. (Mackey et al., 2021) aimed to bridge the knowledge gap regarding the role of Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) in women's empowerment. The study emphasized the transformative power of technology in improving women's lives but highlighted the lack of consensus on how empowerment is defined and measured. The main objective of the paper was to provide a comprehensive overview of the role of technology in promoting women's empowerment and to call for a better understanding and utilization of technology to drive gender equality. (Tang, 2022) focused on exploring the potential of innovative technology and operations in promoting women's economic empowerment and alleviating poverty. The paper reviewed literature and presented case studies from different countries, suggesting that innovative technologies and operations can be effective tools for empowering women economically and reducing poverty. The conclusion highlighted the importance of context and collaboration among stakeholders for maximizing the potential of technology and operations in supporting women's economic empowerment. (Noorali et al., 2022) focused on examining the existing literature on the relationship between women's education and health outcomes in Pakistan. The study found that higher levels of women's education were associated with lower rates of maternal and child mortality, improved access to maternal and child health services, and better nutritional outcomes for women and children. The conclusion highlighted the importance of improving women's access to education as a critical step in enhancing health outcomes in Pakistan, particularly in maternal and child health. (Karp et al., 2020) aimed to evaluate the feasibility of implementing a framework for promoting women's and girls' sexual and reproductive health (SRH) empowerment in sub-Saharan Africa. The study examined factors influencing women's and girls' decisions regarding childbearing and contraception and how external factors impact their ability to achieve their reproductive goals. The research was conducted in Nigeria, Uganda, and Tanzania from 2018 to 2020. The study highlighted the complexity of women's and girls' reproductive choices and the need to address empowerment-related issues in SRH interventions in the region. (Azad et al., 2020) focused on understanding the factors that affect women's and men's access to healthcare in central Malawi. The study found that gender roles significantly influence healthcare access, with women facing more barriers due to social and cultural norms. The authors concluded that efforts to improve healthcare access should address gender inequalities and promote gender equity. Recommendations included promoting women's education and empowerment, challenging cultural norms that restrict women's access to healthcare, and improving access to transportation and financial resources.

2.4. Women empowerment via financial market

(Noor et al., 2021) explore the challenges associated with promoting women's empowerment through entrepreneurship in Pakistan, a country in its nascent stage in this regard. The study focuses on women's decision-making power, access to information, and control over resources as crucial components of women's empowerment. Data was collected through a survey employing a structured questionnaire administered to 120 women in major cities of Pakistan, classified as either housewives or entrepreneur-cum-housewives. The findings indicate that entrepreneurship significantly enhances women's decision-making power compared to their roles as housewives. However, women entrepreneurs face various obstacles, including insufficient governmental support, complex loan procedures from banks, inadequate entrepreneurial education, and limited market awareness. (Vukovic et al., 2023) aim to examine the impact of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) on female entrepreneurship and self-employment in the tourism industry. The research adopts a quantitative methodology to investigate this research question. The study focuses on a sample of 513 women residing in a less-developed rural area in Serbia, with the sample size determined through statistical power analysis to ensure adequate representation of the target population. The results of the study suggest that women in the sample population prioritize self-employment as a pivotal aspect of their empowerment. Self-employment offers various advantages to women, including the ability to control their work schedules, generate income, and attain financial independence. (Iram et al., 2021) conducted a quantitative study that employed a survey questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 400 women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. The researchers utilized regression analysis to examine the data and test their hypotheses. The findings of the study indicate a positive relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions, while heuristic biases were found to have a negative impact on investment decisions. Furthermore, the study suggests that financial literacy can help mitigate heuristic biases and improve investment decisions among women entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

(Aziz et al., 2022) aims to examine the relationship between financial inclusion and women's empowerment in South Asian countries. The study analyzed data from 2004 to 2017 for eight countries in South Asia. The findings demonstrate that financial inclusion plays a significant role in promoting women's empowerment in South Asian countries. Financial inclusion facilitates access to financial services for women, promotes entrepreneurship, and enhances their economic participation and decision-making power.

The study concludes that financial inclusion can effectively contribute to women's empowerment in South Asian countries by providing them with greater economic opportunities and decision-making authority. (Baber, 2020) aims to conduct a comparative analysis of financial inclusion and FinTech in countries with Islamic finance and conventional finance systems. The study selected ten countries that have both financial systems, based on their availability. Data analysis was performed over a seven-year period, from 2011 to 2017, with 2011 as the base year for measuring changes in the population fraction. The findings have significant implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and other stakeholders in the financial sector. The study suggests that valuable lessons can be learned from Islamic finance countries in promoting financial inclusion and women's empowerment. Additionally, it highlights the potential benefits of FinTech in improving access to finance in conventional finance countries, particularly for underserved populations like women. (Mukendi & Manda 2022) examine the role of micro-financial institutions (MFIs) in promoting women's empowerment in Zambia. The study seeks to understand how MFIs affect women's agency and their ability to achieve economic and social empowerment. A qualitative approach was employed, and data was collected through in-depth interviews with MFI staff, MFI clients, and key stakeholders. The study finds that MFIs have contributed to women's economic empowerment through micro-credit provision and business training. It concludes that MFIs have the potential to play a crucial role in promoting women's empowerment in Zambia. However, greater collaboration and coordination among stakeholders are needed to ensure that MFIs effectively address the needs and aspirations of women.

2.5. Research Hypothesis

This study aims to investigate the impact of various factors on women's empowerment in Pakistan. Specifically, three hypotheses are proposed based on existing literature, i.e.

H1: Development of international tourism is likely to have a positive effect on women's living standards and their level of independence.

H2: Gender equality in education, healthcare resources, and labor market reforms is likely to play a crucial role in improving women's empowerment in the country.

H3: Importance of women's access to finance as a critical factor for promoting women's empowerment in Pakistan.

H1 proposes that the development of international tourism is likely to have positive implications for women's living standards and their level of independence. As tourism brings in foreign visitors and generates economic growth, it can create employment opportunities for women, increase their income levels, and enhance their decision-making power within their households. This, in turn, can contribute to their overall empowerment and well-being. H2 suggests that gender equality in education, healthcare resources, and labor market reforms is likely to contribute significantly to women's empowerment in Pakistan. By ensuring equal access to education, improving healthcare facilities, and implementing reforms that address gender disparities in the labor market, women can be empowered to participate more fully in social, economic, and political spheres. H3 emphasizes the critical role of women's access to finance in promoting women's empowerment in a country like Pakistan. Access to financial resources, such as loans, credit facilities, and savings mechanisms, can enable women to start and expand businesses, invest in their education and skills development, and have greater control over their economic activities. By addressing the barriers and constraints that hinder women's access to finance, their economic empowerment can be enhanced, leading to improved overall empowerment levels.

The literature review highlights the empowering impact of tourism on women, emphasizing that increased tourist activity leads to job creation, with many of these employment opportunities directly benefiting women, thereby enhancing their financial independence and self-reliance. The review underscores the importance of providing diverse work opportunities for women, as employment choices empower them and give them greater control over their lives. Additionally, the study emphasizes that investing in women's education and healthcare is instrumental in fostering their intelligence and well-being, further enhancing their decision-making abilities and self-determination. Finally, it underscores the significance of women's financial independence, made possible through access to banking and financial services, as a pivotal step towards greater power and influence in society.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data and Methodology

The human development perspective recognizes the significance of women's role in economic growth, highlighting the connection between women's empowerment and economic development. Information and communication technologies (ICTs) have been identified as a means to promote women's economic independence and access to diverse employment opportunities. This research paper aims to enhance women's economic participation, contribute to societal progress, and shed light on the structural barriers that women still face in achieving these goals. Women's empowerment theory, which focuses on raising awareness and addressing the issue of gender-based discrimination, serves as the foundation for this study. Regarding the data, the analysis will focus on Pakistan's economy as the unit of analysis, utilizing time series data spanning from 1975 to 2020. To address the potential limitations of ordinary least squares estimators, which are sensitive to outliers, and traditional regression techniques, which may yield inaccurate coefficient estimations, robust least squares regression methods is employed.

Several empirical tests have been conducted in a sequential manner. Descriptive statistics provide an overview of the data, while a correlation matrix examines the relationships between variables and identify patterns of association. Robust least squares regression estimate the regression coefficients, with a focus on down-weighting or ignoring the influence of outliers. Granger causality tests investigate whether one time series can be used to predict another, providing insights into potential causal relationships. Additionally, an innovation accounting matrix constructed to account for the contributions of individual variables in explaining the changes in women's empowerment. The regression equation for the study is as follows:

$$WEMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ITOUR + \beta_2 FLFPR + \beta_3 GDH + \beta_4 WAF + \beta_5 GDPPC + \varepsilon \text{ ----- (1)}$$

In this equation:

- WEMP represents women's empowerment, which is the dependent variable.
- ITOUR represents inbound tourism, which is a predictor variable.
- FLFPR represents the female labor force participation rate, which is another predictor variable.
- GDH represents gender disparity in health, which is another predictor variable.
- WAF represents women's access to finance, which is an additional predictor variable.
- GDPPC represents GDP per capita, which is another predictor variable.
- $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and β_5 are the regression coefficients that measure the impact of the respective predictor variables on women's empowerment.
- ε represents the error term, capturing the unexplained variation in the dependent variable.

Through regression analysis, the study aims to estimate the values of the regression coefficients ($\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$) to determine the magnitude and significance of the relationships between the predictor variables (ITOUR, FLFPR, GDH, WAF, GDPPC) and women's empowerment (WEMP). The regression analysis provide insights into how changes in the predictor variables are associated with changes in women's empowerment in the context of Pakistan. Table 1 shows the list of variables for ready reference.

Table 1: List of Variables and Measurement

Variables	Symbols	Unit measurement	Data source
Dependent variable			
Women empowerment Pakistan	WEMP	Women business and law index score (0-100)	World Bank (2022)
Independent variables			
Inbound Tourism	ITOUR	Number of tourists arrival	World Bank (2022)
Female literacy	FL	% of total	World Bank (2022)
Female labor force participation	FLFPR	% of total employment	World Bank (2022)
Gender disparity in health	GDH	Ratio of male to female healthcare expenditures	World Bank (2022)
Women access to finance	WAF	Interaction term used between money supply and women's autonomy	World Bank (2022)
Gross domestic product per capita	GDPPC	US\$	World Bank (2022)

3.2. Data

The empirical examination in this study utilized Pakistan's economy as the unit of analysis. The analysis employed a data sample comprising time series data spanning from 1975 to 2020. For estimation purposes, secondary data was employed, and these data were sourced from the World Development Indicators published by the World Bank in 2022.

3.3. Stationarity of the Data

Time series analysis relies heavily on the stationarity assessment provided by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. Indicative of non-stationarity, the presence of a unit root in a time series dataset may be checked using this test. The purpose of using the ADF test on time series data is to determine whether the data exhibits any statistically significant time variation. If the p-value from the test is less than the significance threshold, the data may be stable, so its statistical features will not change over time. Non-stationarity, when the p-value is larger than the significance threshold, suggests that the data has discernible patterns or seasonality. With the features of the data guaranteed not to change over time, better models and predictions may be made using stationary time series data.

3.4. Robust Least Squares Regression

Statistically, statisticians use robust least squares regression to lessen the weight of outliers and essential data points in a linear regression analysis. The model's parameters are determined via the standard technique of least squares regression by minimizing the squared discrepancies between the actual data and the projected ones. However, if this method is used, outliers might skew the regression findings and provide erroneous parameter estimations. To make the regression analysis more robust to extreme data values, robust least squares regression uses procedures that down weight or give less emphasis to outliers. Huber, Tukey, and Bisquare are popular robust regression methods using various weighting strategies to achieve robustness. When working with real-world data where outliers are widespread, robust least squares regression is very helpful since it ensures that the estimated model represents the bulk of the data points and gives more trustworthy and accurate parameter estimations.

4. RESULTS& DISCUSSION

The mean value of women empowerment is 42.55208, indicating a moderate level of women empowerment in different economic sectors within the Pakistani economy (see, Table 2). The variable ranges from a minimum value of 38.125 to a maximum value of 58.750. The

standard deviation, which measures the spread of the data, is 5.546. The positively skewed distribution suggests the presence of high controversial values. A similar trend can be observed in international tourist arrivals, with a maximum of 1,161,000 tourists visiting Pakistan and a minimum of 369,000. The average number of tourists is 607,395.8, and the standard deviation is 0.5263. Examining female literacy rates in Pakistan, it is observed that, on average, 41 percent of females are literate. The maximum literacy rate is 67.53 percent, while the minimum stands at 23.832 percent. Shifting focus to the female labor force participation rate, it is noted that the maximum rate is 22.454 percent, with an average of 14.720 percent. These figures indicate a relatively low level of female labor force participation.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	WEMP (Index value: 1 low autonomy to 100 high women's autonomy)	ITOUR (in numbers)	FL (% of total female labor force)	FLFPR (% of total female labor force)	GDH (%)	WAF (%)	GDPPC (constant 2015 US\$)
Mean	42.55208	607395.8	41.32361	14.72058	59.50437	9.264583	990.2751
Median	39.68750	430500	43.11405	13.62800	57.37959	9.700000	943.7654
Maximum	58.75000	1161000	67.53713	22.45400	72.94627	9.700000	1473.865
Minimum	38.12500	369000.0	23.83296	10.36800	51.04240	8.100000	588.1596
Std. Dev.	5.546637	269396.3	18.29166	4.035609	4.670696	0.682763	254.6481
Skewness	1.185612	0.526345	0.257782	0.407099	1.350692	-0.996919	0.320112
Kurtosis	3.688633	1.517633	1.293708	1.655429	4.112169	2.099886	2.196368

Note: WEMP shows women empowerment, ITOUR shows inbound tourism, FL shows female literacy, FLFPR shows female labor force participation, GDH shows gender disparity in health, WAF shows women access to finance, and GDPPC shows gross domestic per capita.

Analyzing gender disparity in the health sector, the descriptive statistics reveal a gender disparity of 72.946 percent in terms of the male-to-female ratio. This significant disparity implies a substantial difference in health outcomes between genders. The mean value for gender disparity in health is 59.50437 percent. Furthermore, the data shows that women's access to finance is only 9.70 percent, suggesting limited financial access for women, with an average value of 9.264 percent. Lastly, the per capita income of the country is USD 1,473.865, with an average value of USD 990.2751.

Table 3 displays the correlation matrix, revealing the relationships between various variables. The results indicate a positive correlation between international tourist arrivals and women empowerment. This implies that as the number of foreign tourists visiting a country increases, there is a positive influence on women empowerment. In other words, tourism can contribute to the empowerment of women within a country. Similarly, a positive correlation is observed between the female literacy rate and female labor force participation rate, as well as economic growth and women empowerment. This suggests that higher levels of female literacy and greater female labor force participation contribute to improved women's autonomy and empowerment. Furthermore, economic growth, as indicated by the GDP, is positively associated with women empowerment. This signifies that countries with higher incomes are more likely to experience increased women empowerment. Conversely, there is a negative correlation between women's access to finance and women empowerment. This implies that limited access to financial resources for women negatively impacts their empowerment. On the other hand, the increasing gender disparity in the health sector also has a negative impact on women's autonomy and empowerment.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	WEMP	ITOUR	FL	FLFPR	GDH	WAF	GDPPC
WEMP	1						
ITOUR	0.573882	1					
FL	0.516089	0.966643	1				
FLFPR	0.573171	0.935736	0.934209	1			
GDH	-0.175903	0.528462	0.494637	0.423923	1		
WAF	-0.789922	-0.869638	-0.832912	-0.868227	-0.171517	1	
GDPPC	0.554246	0.884836	0.900674	0.927564	0.294567	-0.839576	1

Note: WEMP shows women empowerment, ITOUR shows inbound tourism, FL shows female literacy, FLFPR shows female labor force participation, GDH shows gender disparity in health, WAF shows women access to finance, and GDPPC shows gross domestic per capita.

Table 4 shows the ADF unit root estimates, which confirmed that whether the variables have a unit root or it possess the stationary series.

Table 4: ADF Unit Root Estimates

Variables	Level	First Difference	Decision
WEMP	0.713 (0.999)	-8.909 (0.000)	I(1)
ITOUR	-2.076 (0.545)	-7.228 (0.000)	I(1)
FL	-2.049 (0.559)	-6.710 (0.000)	I(1)
FLFPR	-3.180 (0.100)	-8.054 (0.000)	I(1)
GDH	-1.510 (0.811)	-6.043 (0.000)	I(1)
WAF	-0.806 (0.807)	-2.747 (0.074)	I(1)
GDPPC	-1.254 (0.886)	-5.704 (0.000)	I(1)

Note: Small bracket shows probability value.

The results confirm that the variables possessed the unit root property. The variables are differenced stationary, I(1) variables. There are two possibilities for estimation, first we have to linearize the data by limiting outliers to get robust parameter estimates. Further, we go for conventional cointegration technique, i.e., Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) to get parameter estimates. Both techniques here used for parameter estimates. Figure 1 displays the influence statistics for the variables. The statistics provide insights into the presence of outliers and influential observations in the model. There are four matrices shown: R student, Hat matrix, DFFITS, and COVRATIO. In terms of R student, there are two outliers identified in the model. These observations deviate significantly from the expected values and have a substantial impact on the overall model fit. The Hat matrix reveals three outliers. The Hat matrix measures the leverage of each observation, indicating how much influence an individual data point has on the model. DFFITS, which measures the difference in fitted values, identifies two outlier observations. These outliers have a significant impact on the estimated values and can heavily influence the overall model results. COVRATIO also identifies two outliers. COVRATIO measures the change in the estimated covariance matrix when a particular observation is excluded. Outliers with high COVRATIO values suggest that removing them from the model can lead to substantial changes in the estimated parameters. The presence of these outliers and influential observations indicates that the model may have potential issues. To further investigate their impact, it is advisable to examine the leverage plot and refer to Figure 2 for additional insights.

Figure 2 presents the leverage plots for the variables. The plot indicates that there are outliers in the variable of international tourist arrivals. Additionally, outliers are observed in the variables of female literacy and female labor force participation rate. These outliers deviate significantly from the expected values and may have a notable impact on the overall model. In contrast, the remaining variables appear to follow a scattered pattern, suggesting that they are relatively closer to the true line. However, there is still some deviation observed, indicating that a simple regression analysis may not be the most appropriate approach. Given the presence of outliers and the scattered nature of the data points, there is a justifiable rationale for employing a robust least square regression instead of a simple regression analysis. A robust regression method can better handle the influence of outliers and provide more reliable estimates for the relationship between variables.

Influence Statistics

Figure 1: Influence Statistics

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 5 presents the results of the robust least square regression. The findings indicate a positive relationship between international tourist arrivals and women's autonomy. The results suggest that as the number of international tourists visiting a country increases, there is a greater potential for women's empowerment. This aligns with previous studies conducted by (A.A.K et al., 2023) and (Mitra et al., 2023), which also found a positive association between international tourism and women's empowerment. The outcomes of these studies are expected to be valuable for local governments and researchers, as they highlight the significance of promoting women's empowerment, gender equality, and international tourism. It emphasizes that an increase in foreign tourist arrivals can contribute positively to women's empowerment within a country. Furthermore, this research observed that international tourism plays a role in reducing gender inequality, although this relationship may not hold true for all countries. Lower-income countries with limited tourism development may not experience the same benefits in reducing gender inequality. Another study by (Elshaer et al., 2021) examines the relationship between tourism and women's empowerment. It investigates how tourism influences women's empowerment levels and how women's empowerment, in turn, impacts their support for tourism. The study concludes that women's empowerment acts as a mediating factor in the relationship between women's autonomy and tourism. The results of this study align with previous findings, indicating a positive relationship between international tourism and women's autonomy.

WEMP vs Variables (Partialled on Regressors)

Figure 2: Leverage Plots

Source: Author's estimate.

Taken together, these results bolster the argument that travel abroad may help advance women's rights. Fostering gender equality and women's rights in tandem with tourist development is crucial since it may lead to enhanced female empowerment. According to the study conducted by (Ali et al., 2023), several noteworthy findings were observed. Firstly, the researchers found that women's representation in the tourism sector remains significantly lower compared to men. This indicates a significant gender disparity in terms of participation and opportunities within the industry. The study thus emphasizes the importance of increasing support and providing more opportunities for women's participation and empowerment in the tourism sector. Additionally, the study identified statistically significant differences in the components of women's empowerment within the tourism sector based on age and educational level. This suggests that age and educational attainment play a role in shaping the level of empowerment experienced by women in the industry. The findings highlight both the progress made in women's empowerment within the tourism sector and the need for further efforts to enhance their representation and empowerment, particularly considering the variations observed based on age and education.

Table 5: Robust Least Squares Regression Estimates

Dependent Variable: WEMP

Method: Robust Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
ITOUR	2.22E-05	9.05E-06	2.450947	0.0142
FL	-0.133945	0.106416	-1.258687	0.2081
FLFPR	0.039337	0.413092	0.095227	0.9241
GDH	-0.575455	0.166993	-3.445984	0.0006
WAF	-5.396757	1.920546	-2.810012	0.0050
GDPPC	-0.010345	0.005294	-1.954153	0.0507
C	128.5270	16.93120	7.591135	0.0000
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.573205	Adjusted R-squared	0.510748	
Rw-squared	0.782644	Adjust Rw-squared	0.782644	

The relationship between gender disparity in health and women's autonomy is negative, indicating that as gender disparity in health increases, more women are likely to experience adverse health outcomes. This implies that governments and policymakers should prioritize reducing gender disparities in both education and health. By addressing these disparities, women's autonomy can be enhanced within a country. These findings align with previous studies, such as the research conducted by (Alisherovna, 2023), which focused on the impact of psychological despotism on gender equality, and suggested that psychological despotism perpetuates harmful gender stereotypes and limits women's autonomy and agency within relationships. Their study demonstrated the negative effects of psychological despotism on women's well-being and empowerment. The article concluded by providing insightful recommendations for addressing psychological despotism and fostering gender equality within families. This supports the notion that there is a negative relationship between gender disparity in health and women's autonomy. Similarly, (Roy & Xiaoling, 2022) found that the gender disparity gap significantly affects women's economic empowerment. The presence of a substantial gender disparity gap directly impacts women's financial independence and autonomy. Closing this gap becomes crucial for women to achieve true economic empowerment, gain financial independence, and have equal opportunities and advantages as men. The study revealed a negative relationship between the gender disparity gap and women's autonomy, further reinforcing the connection between gender disparity in health and women's empowerment.

In a study conducted by (Stollak et al., 2023), researchers found that an increase in the active involvement of women in community meetings was associated with a statistically significant rise in their participation rates in health-related decision-making processes. The study revealed a dose-response effect for two of the six indicators of women's empowerment, with a specific focus on women's autonomy and participation in health-related decision making. The findings highlight the significance of women's increasing participation rates in health-related decision making, as it contributes to their empowerment. The main objective of the study was to examine the impact of women's involvement in community meetings on enhancing their empowerment. The findings, based on focus group discussions (FGDs), indicated that the project being studied had facilitated the process of enhancing women's empowerment. However, the study also identified challenges faced by women in accessing necessary healthcare services for themselves and their children, indicating that there are still areas for improvement. In another study by (Soharwardi et al., 2023), it was found that women's autonomy has a statistically significant influence on the well-being of their children within the household. Surprisingly, enhancing the status of women did not appear to decrease the probability of child malnutrition. However, the study emphasized that when women have the autonomy to make decisions independently, it has a positive impact on the health of their children. The study suggests that the lack of independence and autonomy among women in society negatively affects the health outcomes of their children.

The relationship between women's access to finance and women's autonomy is negative, indicating that when women have limited financial opportunities and access to capital markets, their autonomy significantly decreases. This finding is supported by a study conducted by (Nguyenthe & Le, 2023), which identified various factors contributing to the development of women's authority. The study revealed that women's ownership of property has a greater impact on nonfinancial decision-making authority compared to financial decisions. Specifically, women's land ownership was found to have the highest influence on decision-making regarding their children. Ensuring equal access and control over land for women is crucial for promoting intergenerational transfer of benefits and opportunities. In line with these findings, (Kumar et al., 2023) suggest that educational institutions should prioritize the development of financial literacy and digital skills among students. Their study emphasizes the relationship between various factors, such as skills, financial decision-making, and perceived financial well-being, and their cumulative impact on individuals' ability to navigate

environmental challenges and manage socioeconomic pressures effectively. The study highlights the significance of recognizing the relationship between skills, financial decision-making, and well-being in the workplace. Companies can support their employees' financial well-being by offering training programs, resources, and tools that enhance financial literacy and promote effective decision-making. (Malik et al., 2022) conducted a study involving women entrepreneurs and found that financial stability had a positive influence on their ability to acquire new knowledge and enhance their skills over time. When female entrepreneurs had a solid financial foundation, they were more likely to invest in self-improvement activities such as workshops, acquiring new knowledge, and honing their abilities. This study highlights the positive impact of financial stability on learning and skill development among female entrepreneurs. Another study by (Oladipo et al., 2023) concluded that women who pursue home-based businesses can effectively reduce the performance gap between male and female entrepreneurs. The findings of this study emphasize the importance of providing women with options and opportunities to engage in self-employment and home-based businesses. Supporting women's choices and creating an enabling environment for their entrepreneurial pursuits is crucial for promoting gender equality and inclusive economic development.

The negative relationship between GDP per capita (economic growth) and women empowerment suggests that economic growth alone does not necessarily lead to increased women's autonomy or economic power. This may indicate the presence of social barriers or factors that limit women's empowerment in a country. This finding aligns with a study conducted by (Press, 2023), which investigated the impact of women's labor force participation on economic growth. The study revealed a negative correlation between economic growth and female labor force participation, suggesting that higher levels of economic growth may not necessarily lead to increased women's engagement in the workforce. This negative relationship between economic growth and female labor force participation has implications for women's empowerment. On the other hand, a study conducted by (Bayramov et al., 2023) focused on the involvement of women in the labor force and their economic empowerment in the Commonwealth of Independent countries. Their analysis showed a positive correlation between economic growth and women's participation in the labor force, indicating that as the economy grows, more women actively engage in the workforce. This finding suggests that the relationship between economic growth and female labor force participation may vary across different contexts. (Machmud et al., 2023) emphasized the significance of empowering women in contemporary society, highlighting its role in political stability and economic growth. Their study underlines the importance of challenging traditional gender roles and providing women with opportunities to contribute to progress and development. (Singh et al., 2022) highlighted the positive effects of investments in education and training on various aspects of sustainable development, including economic growth and socioeconomic well-being. This suggests that prioritizing education and training can contribute to women's empowerment and overall development. (Sasmoko et al., 2022) emphasized the importance of women's political empowerment, economic growth, and better immunization coverage in achieving sustainable healthcare. Their study found that unstable employment for women was associated with higher child mortality rates, emphasizing the need to provide women with equal opportunities in the labor market to effectively meet their family's healthcare needs.

The robust statistics indicate that the R-squared value is 0.573205. This value represents the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. In this case, the R-squared value of 0.573205 suggests that approximately 57.3 percent of the variation in the dependent variable can be accounted for by the independent variables in the model. A higher R-squared value indicates a better fit of the model to the data. In this context, the R-squared value of 0.573205 suggests that the model has a reasonably good fit, as it can explain more than half of the variation in the dependent variable. However, it is important to note that there may still be unexplained factors contributing to the remaining 42.7 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Therefore, further analysis and consideration of other relevant variables may be necessary to enhance the model's explanatory power. Table 6 shows the FMOLS estimates for ready reference.

Table 6: FMOLS Estimates

Dependent Variable: WEMP				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ITOUR	2.61E-05	1.32E-05	1.972322	0.0555
FL	-0.148359	0.155561	-0.953699	0.3460
FLFPR	0.286425	0.605641	0.472929	0.6388
GDH	-0.771505	0.244927	-3.149935	0.0031
GDPPC	-0.014439	0.008082	-1.786705	0.0816
WAF	-5.055043	2.806964	-1.800893	0.0793
C	135.8893	24.92789	5.451299	0.0000
R-squared	0.754487	Mean dependent var		42.64628
Adjusted R-squared	0.717660	S.D. dependent var		5.567662
Diagnostic Tests				
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	0.776	Prob. value		0.678
Heteroskedasticity Test	2.488	Prob. value		0.074

The results of the study suggest that the impact of inbound tourism on women's empowerment is twofold. On one hand, it has a positive effect by reducing gender disparities in healthcare. This means that when a country experiences an increase in inbound tourism, it tends to allocate more resources and attention to healthcare services for women, thus narrowing the gender gap in health-related outcomes. This could include improved access to healthcare facilities, better healthcare information and services, and a general reduction in health-related disparities between men and women. On the other hand, the results also reveal a more complex relationship. They indicate that a nation's income level and the accessibility of financial resources for women play significant roles in determining women's empowerment. In other words, if a country has a higher income level and ensures that women have adequate access to financial resources, this positively impacts women's empowerment. Conversely, inadequate financial access for women can hinder their empowerment. In summary, the findings suggest that while inbound tourism can be a catalyst for reducing gender disparities in health and, consequently, promoting women's empowerment, it should be complemented with efforts to enhance a nation's income and ensure that women have equitable access to financial resources to achieve comprehensive and sustainable improvements in women's empowerment.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study conducted in Pakistan aimed to examine the determinants of women empowerment and their relationship with economic development. The analysis utilized data from 1975 to 2020. The findings revealed that inbound tourism has a positive impact on women empowerment, suggesting that the presence of tourism activities can contribute to empowering women in the country. Conversely, gender disparity in health, limited women's access to finance, and inadequate economic growth were found to decrease women's autonomy. The study highlights the significant role of various factors in shaping women empowerment in Pakistan. The following are the policy recommendations of the study, i.e.,

- I. Governments should prioritize the development of the tourism sector by implementing policies that promote innovation and create a conducive environment for women's participation in the industry. This can be achieved through initiatives such as providing training and mentorship programs specifically tailored for women in tourism.
- II. Promote gender equality and women's rights by enacting and enforcing policies that prioritize gender equality in all spheres of society. This includes ensuring equal access to opportunities and resources for women in the cultural tourism sector. By creating an inclusive and supportive environment, women can fully contribute to and benefit from the tourism industry.
- III. Foster environmental education and awareness among women by implementing educational programs that emphasize the importance of environmental conservation and sustainable practices. These programs should empower women to become environmentally conscious and actively participate in initiatives aimed at preserving natural resources.
- IV. Increase investment in female education and environmental initiatives to improve literacy rates among girls and women. By allocating resources for education, particularly in underserved areas, governments can enhance women's access to knowledge and skills that are crucial for their empowerment and active participation in the economy.
- V. Implement gender-specific training and awareness campaigns that encourage women and men to garner support from their family members and foster a stronger entrepreneurial mindset among women. By promoting entrepreneurship and providing the necessary support, women can overcome social and economic barriers and achieve economic independence.
- VI. Address the gender pay gap by implementing policies and regulations that ensure equal pay for equal work. By reducing pay disparities between men and women, governments can create a fair and equitable economic landscape that empowers women financially.
- VII. Enhance women's financial literacy skills by providing opportunities for them to participate in seminars and courses focused on financial knowledge. By improving their understanding of finances and money management, women can make informed decisions, enhance their lifestyles, and fulfill their financial obligations promptly.
- VIII. Promote the establishment of a cooperative network among women business owners, enabling them to combine their resources and share insights to provide assistance to other women entrepreneurs. By fostering collaboration and mutual support, women can overcome challenges and collectively contribute to economic growth and development.
- IX. Governments should adopt financial policies that specifically cater to women entrepreneurs and offer innovative financing alternatives for this group. By providing targeted financial support and access to capital, governments can facilitate the growth and sustainability of women-owned businesses.
- X. Encourage women's participation in decision-making processes by promoting gender diversity in financial institutions and ensuring that women have a seat at the table when designing and implementing financial policies. By including women's perspectives and expertise, governments can make more inclusive and effective policy decisions that benefit society as a whole.

These policy recommendations aim to address the barriers and challenges that hinder women's empowerment in Pakistan and promote an environment that fosters gender equality, economic participation, and sustainable development. By implementing these measures, governments can create opportunities for women to thrive, contribute to the economy, and ultimately drive social and economic progress in the country.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Ali, M., Grabarski, M. K., & Konrad, A. M. (2022). Women in hospitality and tourism: a study of the top-down and bottom-up dynamics. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 34(4), 1448-1469.
2. Alisherovna, T. M. (2023). Problems of Psychological Despotism of Gender Equality in Problem Families. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(3), 146-152.
3. Asadullah, M. N., & Kambhampati, U. (2021). Feminization of farming, food security and female empowerment. *Global Food Security*, 29, 100532.
4. Azad, A. D., Charles, A. G., Ding, Q., Trickey, A. W., & Wren, S. M. (2020). The gender gap and healthcare: associations between gender roles and factors affecting healthcare access in Central Malawi, June–August 2017. *Archives of Public Health*, 78(1), 1-11.
5. Aziz, F., Sheikh, S. M., & Shah, I. H. (2022). Financial inclusion for women empowerment in South Asian countries. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 30(4), 489-502.
6. Aziz, F., Sheikh, S. M., & Shah, I. H. (2022). Financial inclusion for women empowerment in South Asian countries. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 30(4), 489-502.
7. Baber, H. (2020). Financial inclusion and FinTech: A comparative study of countries following Islamic finance and conventional finance. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, 12(1), 24-42.
8. Bhandari, R. C., Thapa, L., & Thapa, A. Homestay Tourism Promoting Local Entrepreneurship in Nepal: A Case Study of Sirubari Village, Syangja.
9. Braverman-Bronstein, A., Ortigoza, A. F., Vidaña-Pérez, D., Barrientos-Gutiérrez, T., Baldovino-Chiquillo, L., Bilal, U., ... & Roux, A. V. D. (2023). Gender inequality, women's empowerment, and adolescent birth rates in 363 Latin American cities. *Social Science & Medicine*, 317, 115566.
10. Cajamarca, G., & Herskovic, V. (2022). Understanding experiences and expectations from active, independent older women in Chile towards technologies to manage their health. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 166, 102867.
11. De Brauw, A., Kramer, B., & Murphy, M. (2021). Migration, labor and women's empowerment: Evidence from an agricultural value chain in Bangladesh. *World Development*, 142, 105445.
12. Elshaer, I., Moustafa, M., Sobaih, A. E., Aliedan, M., & Azazz, A. M. (2021). The impact of women's empowerment on sustainable tourism development: Mediating role of tourism involvement. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 38, 100815.
13. Ghosh, M. K., Hasan, S. S., Fariha, R., Bari, M. O., & Parvin, M. A. (2021). Women empowerment through agriculture in chapainawabganj, Bangladesh. *European Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 3(1), 153-160.
14. Haq, Z. U., Ullah, Z., & Sajjad. (2019). Households' participation in and expenditure on recreation and tourism in Pakistan. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 24(3), 206-218.
15. Hornset, N., & de Soysa, I. (2022). Does Empowering Women in Politics Boost Human Development? An Empirical Analysis, 1960–2018. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 23(2), 291-318.
16. Iram, T., Iqbal, N., Qazi, R., & Saleem, S. (2021). Nexus between Financial Literacy, Investment Decisions and Heuristic Biases of Women Entrepreneurs—A Way forward for Women Empowerment. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 41(1), 221-234.
17. Jackman, M. (2022). The effect of tourism on gender equality in the labour market: Help or hindrance?. In *Women's Studies International Forum* (Vol. 90, p. 102554). Pergamon.
18. Karp, C., Wood, S. N., Galadanci, H., Kibira, S. P. S., Makumbi, F., Omoluabi, E., ... & Moreau, C. (2020). 'I am the master key that opens and locks': Presentation and application of a conceptual framework for women's and girls' empowerment in reproductive health. *Social Science & Medicine*, 258, 113086.
19. Kinnaird, V., & Hall, D. (1996). Understanding tourism processes: A gender-aware framework. *Tourism management*, 17(2), 95-102.
20. Kumar, P., Pillai, R., Kumar, N., & Tabash, M. I. (2023). The interplay of skills, digital financial literacy, capability, and autonomy in financial decision making and well-being. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 23(1), 169-183.
21. Kusumawardhani, N., Pramana, R., Saputri, N. S., & Suryadarma, D. (2023). Heterogeneous impact of internet availability on female labor market outcomes in an emerging economy: Evidence from Indonesia. *World Development*, 164, 106182.
22. Machmud, T. V., Lolowang, I., & Andries, F. (2023). WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT IN MONA LISA SMILE MOVIE SCRIPT. *JoTELL: Journal of Teaching English, Linguistics, and Literature*, 2(1), 63-75.
23. Mackey, A., & Petrucka, P. (2021). Technology as the key to women's empowerment: a scoping review. *BMC Women's Health*, 21, 1-12.
24. Malik, R. A., Batool, H., & Afzal, M. (2022). Determinants Of Women Entrepreneurship Mindset In Achieving Sustainable Development: A Case Study Of Lahore, Pakistan. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(12), 1665-1688.
25. Mitra, S. K., Chattopadhyay, M., & Chatterjee, T. K. (2023). Can tourism development reduce gender inequality?. *Journal of Travel Research*, 62(3), 563-577.
26. Mubeen, S., Hye, Q. M. A., Shahid, M. H., & Rehan, R. (2022). The nexus among family business, household finances and women empowerment: Evidence from PDHS 2017-18. *Nurture*, 16(2), 90-102.
27. Mubeen, S., Shahid, M. H., & Hye, Q. M. A. (2022). The relationship between the empowerment of women and preferences related to fertility in Pakistan. *Journal of Social Economics Research*, 9(2), 121-136.
28. Mukendi, S., & Manda, S. (2022). Micro-financial institutions and processes of women empowerment in Zambia. *World Development Perspectives*, 28, 100466.
29. Nasridinbekovna, K. N. (2022). The role of women's personnel in the development of the national economy of uzbekistan: social and political status (1917-1940). *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 4, 110-117.
30. Naz, A., & Ashraf, F. (2020). The Relationship between Higher Education and Women Empowerment in Pakistan. *UMT Education Review*, 3(2), 65-84.
31. Nguyen, M., & Le, K. (2023). The impacts of women's land ownership: Evidence from Vietnam. *Review of Development Economics*, 27(1), 158-177.

32. Noor, S., Isa, F. M., & Nor, L. M. (2021). Women empowerment through women entrepreneurship: a comparison between women entrepreneurs and fulltime housewife in Pakistan. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 14(2), 347-363.
33. Noorali, A. A., Inam, M., Shahbaz, H., Rauf, H., Aamir, F. B., Khalid, F., ... & Haider, A. H. (2022). A nationwide virtual research education program for medical students in Pakistan: methodological framework, feasibility testing, and outcomes. *Frontiers in public health*, 9, 812130.
34. Oladipo, O., Platt, K., & Shim, H. S. (2023). Female entrepreneurs managing from home. *Small Business Economics*, 61, 447-464.
35. Payramov, V., Islamli, N., & Mammadov, E. (2023). Assessment of Gender Equality & Women's Empowerment in the Post-Soviet Space. Online available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4323803 (accessed on 2nd December, 2023).
36. Press, C. E. S. D. (2023). Gender Equality & Women's Empowerment in the Post-Soviet Space: Challenges and Perspectives. Online available at: <https://cesd.az/y/panel/uploads/35347062453-CESDGenderEqualityWomenEmpowermentPaper.pdf> (accessed on 1st December, 2023).
37. Reshi, I. A., & Sudha, T. (2022). Women Empowerment: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Economic, Business, Accounting, Agriculture Management and Sharia Administration (IJEBAAS)*, 2(6), 1353-1359.
38. Rettig, E. M., Fick, S. E., & Hijmans, R. J. (2018). The Female Empowerment Index (FEMI): Spatial and temporal variation in women's empowerment in Nigeria. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 25(2), 152-177.
39. Roy, C. K., & Xiaoling, H. (2022). Achieving SDG 5, gender equality and empower all women and girls, in developing countries: how aid for trade can help?. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 49(6), 930-959.
40. Samad, S., & Alharthi, A. (2022). Untangling factors influencing women entrepreneurs' involvement in tourism and its impact on sustainable tourism development. *Administrative Sciences*, 12(2), 52.
41. Saqfalhait, N., AbdAlla Spetan, K., Awad-Warrad, T., & Alomari, M. W. (2023). Trade liberalization and women empowerment in the Arab countries. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 15(3), 232-248.
42. Sasmoko, Shabnam, Handayani, W., Nassani, A. A., Haffar, M., & Zaman, K. (2022). Do precarious female employment and political autonomy affect the under-5 mortality rate? Evidence from 166 countries. *Plos one*, 17(6), e0269575.
43. Sayira, T., Andrews, H., & Ayesha, Q. U. A. (2021). Are Women Empowered Producers of Tourism in Pakistan?. *Women in Tourism in Asian Muslim Countries*, 81-96.
44. Seyfi, S., Hall, C. M., Saarinen, J., & Vo-Thanh, T. (2023). Do international sanctions help or inhibit justice and sustainability in tourism?. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 31, 2716-2733.
45. Singh, H. P., Singh, A., Alam, F., & Agrawal, V. (2022). Impact of sustainable development goals on economic growth in Saudi Arabia: Role of education and training. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14119.
46. Soharwardi, M. A., Ahmadzai, N., Khan, M. H. N., Kumbhar, M. I., Riaz, A., Malik, F., ... & Afzal, M. (2023). Measuring Women Empowerment And Its Contribution Towards Child's Nutritional Status: An Evidence From Developing Regions. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 7, 633-652.
47. Stollak, I., Valdez, M., Story, W. T., & Perry, H. B. (2023). Reducing inequities in maternal and child health in rural Guatemala through the CBIO+ approach of Curamericas: 8. Impact on women's empowerment. *International journal for equity in health*, 21(2), 1-14.
48. Syed, Q. R., Bhowmik, R., Adedoyin, F. F., Alola, A. A., & Khalid, N. (2022). Do economic policy uncertainty and geopolitical risk surge CO2 emissions? New insights from panel quantile regression approach. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(19), 27845-27861.
49. Tang, C. S. (2022). Innovative technology and operations for alleviating poverty through women's economic empowerment. *Production and Operations Management*, 31(1), 32-45.
50. Vukovic, D. B., Petrovic, M., Maiti, M., & Vujko, A. (2023). Tourism development, entrepreneurship and women's empowerment—Focus on Serbian countryside. *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 9(3), 417-437.
51. Wang, C., & Naveed, A. (2021). Can Women Empowerment Explain Cross-Country Differences in Inequality? A Global Perspective. *Social Indicators Research*, 158(2), 667-697.
52. Wei, W., Sarker, T., Żukiewicz-Sobczak, W., Roy, R., Alam, G. M., Rabbany, M. G., ... & Aziz, N. (2021). The influence of women's empowerment on poverty reduction in the rural areas of Bangladesh: Focus on health, education and living standard. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(13), 6909.
53. Wejnert, B. (2021). Effects of Market-Based Development on Women's Empowerment: Impact on Families. *Marriage & Family Review*, 57(6), 473-502.
54. World Bank (2022). World development indicators, World Bank, Washington D.C.
55. Zhang, J., & Zhang, Y. (2020). Tourism and gender equality: An Asian perspective. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 85, 103067.
56. Zhang, Y., Xu, S., & Zhang, J. (2022). Examining the Relationship between Tourism and Gender Equality: Evidence from Asia. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12156.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.